

The Effect of Socioeconomic Status on Self-Concept among the Married Women Admitted to the Health Centers in Eastern Tehran

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Abstract: Self-concept has attracted the attention of the psychologists and sociologists in recent decade. Recent cultural and structural changes, economic transformations, and women's involvement in earning income and providing educational opportunities have led to changes in the formation of self-concept among women. Since the determining factors in the formation of self-concept are not completely revealed yet, the main goal of this research is to analyze the kind of women's self-concept with respect to their socioeconomic status. The research framework is selected based on the symbolic interaction theory and resource theory. The population in this survey included married women who were admitted to the health centers in eastern districts of Tehran. 282 members of the sample group were selected randomly. According to the findings, there is a meaningful relationship between participants' self-concept and a few variables such as their mother's education level, father's education level, their own education level, their father's income, mother's employment, and their own employment. This relationship between their self-concept and variables such as mother's income and their own income is not statistically significant.

Keywords: Self-Concept, Self-Esteem, Excising Self-Concept, Ideal Self-Concept.

Introduction

In the present century, there are many fundamental questions about the human in modern day including the nature of women and the issues concerning them (Dehnavi, 2005). Although women compose half of Iran's population, many issues related to them are ignored or marginalized (Navabinejad, 2006). Underestimation of women's abilities is the result of discrimination, ignorance, superstition and prejudices. The existing realities in the society show the serious social damages of girls and women. Divorce, delinquency, addiction, running away from home, and suicide are vivid examples of social psychological damages which seems to be deeply rooted in educational culture in which an individual has grown up (Rajaeepour & Kargaran; 2003). In Iran's society, family is still the most fundamental institution (Zanjanizadeh Azazi & Amiri Torshizi, 2005). Studies indicated that there is a relationship between family performance and self-concept of family members (Dibajnia, 2004). Family and parents' relations, socioeconomic and cultural status of the family are the factors forming the self-concept (Dehnavi, 2005). Any confusion inside the family would result in feeling of insecurity, low self-esteem and illogical self-concept (Doman, 2000).

The problems, insufficiencies and necessities related to the women were of the focus in societies and the researchers consider them for ages (Dehnavi, 2005). In recent decades, international communities and researchers in human science have paid much attention to the women and their problems in so far as the United Nations considered women problems in its evaluation of the countries' indices of human development (Houminfar, 2003). The results of the studies indicated that women socialization in patriarch society is in such a way that the women know themselves

more menial than men. In such a society, the more prevalent this social perception, the less self-respect is among women, and less competent they think of themselves (Mohseni Tabrizi & Seyedan, 2004). Durkheim believed that in such a society, women spend most of their times at home and feel no autonomy because they appear in the society less than men (Durkheim cited by Zanjani Azazi, 2005). This lack of autonomy is affective in negative self-concept among women. According to Weber, a woman with no developed thought is like a child who is not seeking growth and is restricted in the family (Zanjani Azazi & Tarshizi, 2005). We see that the women are humiliated at home and cannot say their opinions freely; these problems are due to the highlighted mental perspective that the women have formed about their own (Mohseni Tabrizi & Seyedan, 2004). Considering the important role of parents in developing women's self-concept and importance of its socioeconomic status, we analyzed the effect of socioeconomic status on married women's self-concept. Despite the large number of studies on women's issues, few studies have delved in to the socioeconomic status on married women's self-concept. The study about the individuals in a society is meaningful in social structure of that society. Since we cannot ignore the effect of culture on self-concept in a society, it requires a separate scientific investigation in any society in that respect. That is why it sounds useless to rely heavily on the findings of other societies as they have a different culture (Keshavarz, 2002).

Self-concept refers to any thoughts and feelings an individual has about him/herself that can lead his or her opinion and action in various social fields. A menial or equal-to-men self-concept makes the individual's conception toward him/herself as a person captured in natural determination or active in limited fields. Accepting these issues in the family cause women to be placed in the lower position than men in the society and force them to accept such a situation because they are not allowed to improve. A passive woman would remain dependent and cannot be a suitable wife because she only takes care of her husband but cannot provide any complementary action or opinion or any intellectual motivation for her husband and in such a marriage the husband makes no effort anymore (Zanjani Azazi & Amiri Torshizi, 2005). Women, who feel themselves more menial than men, cannot nurture independent active persons because a passive dependent person is unable to educate an active independent one. A couple with similar abilities will help develop themselves and have mutual understanding toward each other and bring up children with recognized skills (Zanjani Azazi & Amiri Torshizi, 2005).

If women are considered lower than men and men are superior to women, this may lead to unbalanced growth in men's and women's personality. Hence, analyzing socioeconomic status, we are trying to identify the effects of these factors, as a part of effective factors in forming women's self-concept, to the families.

Self-concept is the general thoughts and feelings the individual have to refer to him/her as a subjective recognition. It is divided in to three parts: the existing (real) self, the ideal (wishing) self, the pretended self. We have analyzed the first and the second ones.

- The existing (real) self: it is an image we have of ourselves in our mind.
- The ideal (wishing) self: it is an image of what we like to be.
- Socioeconomic status is a combination index including both work experience and individual's socioeconomic status comparing with others in the society. It is classified in three ranks: high, middle, low. We can evaluate the socioeconomic status using many methods including direct and indirect indexes. The direct and indirect indexes include monthly salary, education and individuals' job in the society; these are the older evaluation indices of socioeconomic status. The amount of asset an individual owns is of the indirect and new indices used in the studies of developing and evaluating individuals' health.

Research Background

In a study by Kavousian & Kadivar (2005) entitled "the role of some familial factors in familial self-concept among the high school students, 3935 students were selected out of all Iran's high school students. The findings indicated that there is a meaningful correlation between mother's employment, father's level of education and the self-concept but there is no meaningful relationship between mother's education and children's self-concept. They found out that the girls' and boys' familial self-concepts are affected by the family %49 and %35 respectively; i.e. there is a relationship between women's self-concept and familial factors. Another finding is that the girls are more affected by the familial factors because of their sociable nature.

Pourhossein (2002) have carried out a study under the title of "the analysis of self-concept among the children of 6 – 12 years old and its relationship with gender and social cast. The findings revealed that the parents' income, education, and job are of the socioeconomic factors that affect the self-concept. Karimzadeh & Mohseni (2005) in an article called "the relation between self-concept and educational success of girl high school students at second grade in physics and human science", stated that self-concept affects the students' success (Karimzadeh & Mohseni, 2005). In an article called "a comparative evaluation of self-concept among freshmen and seniors at Shahid Beheshti

University" in 2005, Dibajnia expressed that there is no relationship between self-concept and marital status, age, gender, and education (Dibajnia, 2005).

Research Theoretical Framework

In this study, we used the theories of symbolic interaction school of thought to explain self-concept since the individual's self-concept is formed based on action and reaction of individual with the society not excluding the family. The interaction school focuses on two factors of language and communication and on the belief that the individuals can learn a culture by language and communication. The communications would enable the individual to improve self-recognition (Dastranj as cited in Smith and Priston, 2010).

As any individual has the first communications with the parents, the family and the type of relation is effective on self-concept. The resource theory was used for women's socioeconomic and cultural status. This theory is based on three hypotheses:

- 1) Any human would try continually to satisfy the needs and is eager to achieve the goals.
- 2) Many of the human needs would be met by social interaction.
- 3) The constant exchange of resources is done by this interaction to satisfy the individuals' needs and achieve the goals. In this theory, the authority in decision-making is in the hand of a person who owns the biggest and the most valuable resources.

According to the resource theory, we can say that women with high level of education, income, and satisfactory employment are more active in the society. This presence in society and financial resources one earns cause a different self-concept comparing with the women with low level of education, lower income or even unemployed.

Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between women's employment and their self-concept.

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between women's income and their self-concept.

Hypothesis 3: There is a relationship between women's level of education and their self-concept.

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their fathers' income.

Hypothesis 5: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's income.

Hypothesis 6: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's level of education.

Hypothesis 7: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their father's level of education.

Hypothesis 8: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's employment.

Research Theoretical Model

The Roger's self-concept scale was used to collect data; the scale which was developed by Carl Rodger from 1938 to 1957. It includes two forms of "A and B" with 25 pairs of attributes. The "form A" shows self-concept in such a way that the subject evaluated him/herself based on the view toward each attribute.

The "form B" is similar to "form A" and the subject evaluated him/herself based on the ideal self-concept in future. The following diagram shows the relation between research independent variables and self-concept. Based on the diagram, one can say that the women's self-concept and women's socioeconomic status and their parents' socioeconomic status affect their self-concept.

Figure 1. The Roger's self-concept scale.

Materials and Methods

This study is a quantitative one and a survey in respect to research typology. The population of this research included 1260 married women who have married at least for one year, live in Tehran, and are admitted in health centers – dental clinics – in eastern Tehran.

Sampling and Sample Size

The Roger's self-concept scale has been used in various studies. The validity of this scale was evaluated (correlation coefficient of 0.81 and reliability index of 0.89). Tehran is divided into four districts by the Ministry of Health: North, South, East, and West. The Eastern Tehran Health Centers were selected randomly where 23 centers were located. One of the centers called 17-Shahrivar health center was randomly selected. Seven women were daily admitted to this center which amounted to 1260 in a 6-month period. Out of them, based on Morgan-Krejci's sample size table, 297 were selected. The scale was administered to all of them and except fifteen, which were disregarded as they were left unanswered or partially answered, 282 were selected to be analyzed.

Results

Out of all the respondents to the self-concept scales, those with the age range 35–39 had the highest frequency (31.6%). The age group 50-54 had the lowest frequency (6.4%) which seems to be natural due to the dispersion of the population in Iran. Taking their married life period into consideration, those with 10-14 years showed the highest frequency and those with 36 and above showed the lowest frequency. The women who held BA (36.2%) and those of them who were illiterate (7%) had the highest and lowest frequency respectively. The highest and lowest frequency for the level of education among respondents' mothers was primary school certificate (33.3%) and associate degree (2.8%). This index among respondents' fathers was primary school certificate (39%) and MA (7%). Out of 282 respondent's mothers, 244 were unemployed and 38 were employed. This index among the respondents themselves was 110 and 172 respectively.

Testing Hypotheses

To collect data, Roger's self-concept scale was administered with the score varying from 0 to 10 in three levels: Positive and Normal Level (0-7 scores), Average Level (7 – 10 scores), and negative and weak Level (10+). To investigate the relationship between the variables, Somers' correlation coefficient was adopted in which the negative index shows a negative correlation. That is, the lower the score, the higher the self-concept level and the other way round.

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between women's employment and their self-concept

The relationship between these two variables was studied through a contingency table (2 by 2 table), Chi Square, and Cramer's V Correlation Coefficient. The result of hypothesis testing based on the chi square index and level of significance (Sig > 0.01) indicated that there is a significant relationship between women's employment and their self-concept with more than 99% probability. This means that employment can have impact on their self-concept.

Table 1. The relationship between two variables.

Chi Square	Women's employment
X^2	3.578
Cramer's V Correlation Coefficient	0.113
Sig.	0.167

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between women's income and their self-concept

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to the third table of Somers, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.067 and the level of significance (Sig. > 0.05). That is, there is not a significant relationship between women's income and their self-concept. It is worth mentioning that the present conclusion is the result of this sample size and larger sample might change the result.

Table 2. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Women's income	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.067
	Sig.	0.131

Hypothesis 3: There is a relationship between women's level of education and their self-concept

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to the fourth table of Somers, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.086 and the level of significance (Sig. = 0.05). It, therefore, indicated that there is a significant relationship between women's level of education and their self-concept with more than 95% probability. This means that the level of education can have an impact on their self-concept.

Table 3. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Women's level of education	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.087
	Sig.	0.050

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their fathers' income

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to the fifth table of Somers, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.106 and the level of significance (Sig. < 0.05). It, therefore, indicated that there is a significant relationship between women's self-concept and their fathers' income with more than 95% probability. This means that their fathers' income can have an impact on their self-concept.

Table 4. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Fathers' income	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.106
	Sig.	0.025

Hypothesis 5: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's income

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to Somers' table 6, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.081 and the level of significance (Sig. > 0.05). That is, there is not a significant relationship between women's self-concept and their mothers' income.

Table 5. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Mothers' income	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.081
	Sig.	0.133

Hypothesis 6: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's level of education

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to Somers' table 1, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.147 and the level of significance (Sig. < 0.05). That is, there is a significant relationship between women's self-concept and their mothers' level of education with more than 99% probability.

Table 6. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Mothers' level of education	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.147
	Sig.	0.000

Hypothesis 7: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their father's level of education

The relationship between these two variables was investigated using contingency table and Somers' correlation coefficient d. According to Somers' table 2, correlation coefficient index was calculated to be -0.136 and the level of significance (Sig. < 0.05). That is, there is a significant relationship between women's self-concept and their fathers' level of education with more than 99% probability.

Table 7. The relationship between two variables.

Somers' Correlation Coefficient d	Fathers' level of education	
Self-concept	Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.136
	Sig.	0.003

Hypothesis 8: There is a relationship between women's self-concept and their mother's employment

The relationship between these two variables was studied through a contingency table (2 by 2 table), Chi Square, and Cramer's V Correlation Coefficient. The result of hypothesis testing, based on the Chi Square index and level of significance (Sig > 0.01), indicated that there is a significant relationship between women's self-concept and their mothers' employment with more than 99% probability. This means that mothers' employment can have an impact on their self-concept.

Table 8. The relationship between two variables.

Chi Square	Mothers' employment	
Self-concept	X ²	11.017
	Cramer's V Correlation Coefficient	0.198
	Sig.	0.004

Discussion and Conclusion

According to the research findings, there is a relationship between parents' level of education and mother's employment, between women's level of education and their employment, and between father's income and women's self-concept. According to the findings, the more desirable their socioeconomic status is, the closer their self-concept to the ideal one. These results were in harmony with the findings of two studies: one by Jafari (2005) indicating that there is a meaningful relationship between education, employment, job, income and belief (woman is inferior to a man), and the other by Kavousian & Kadivar (2005) revealing that there is a meaningful correlation between mother's employment, father's education level and self-concept. Dibajnia also concluded that there is no meaningful relation between mother's level of education and self-concept. Based on Kavousian & Kadivar's research, high school students' self-concept has a significant correlation with fathers' level of education in three groups of high school diploma, below and above it. Pourhossein (2002) declared that the parents' level of education

is effective in self-concept; there is also no relationship between self-concept among the women under study and their income. This result is not consistent with the results of Jafari's research. In addition, there is no relationship between self-concept and mother's income. This is also not in harmony with Pourhossein's research where they found out that there is no relationship between socioeconomic status, job, parents' income and self-concept.

Suggestions

1. Women should be empowered through steps in which the individuals are to adopt activities to overcome the barriers of progress; the steps which enable women to act on their own. These steps are:

- Upgrading one's level of education,
- Training women in their related courses,
- Trying to change the women's attitude in such a way that they do not think the current situation as unchangeable so that they encourage the change in them. So, they should try to adopt the tools for this change,
- Making men and women aware of the values and abilities of women and their effective role in family and society. This would be helpful to modify the public culture of the society and make the women's active partnership possible in social affairs.

2. New behavioral paradigms effective in socialization process are to be introduced through ministry of education, mass media by advertising and presenting appropriate personal characteristics.

3. It is recommended that the researchers consider other factors in familial aspect such as effect of gender work division on self-concept. The studies on women's self-concept have not been applied in action enough so it should be more practical.

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